

EXPRESSION OF SPEECH ACT TYPES IN THE TEXT OF LETTERS OF RECOMMENDATION IN FRENCH LANGUAGE

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Abstract. This article presents a study aimed at analyzing the French language recommendation documents from a pragmatic perspective. The article examines in detail the importance of the development of the state language and official and departmental business documents, as well as the specific features of the recommendation document and its expression in French texts. Recommendation documents are prepared with the aim of recommending a person for a position or membership in organizations, and their content provides information about the candidate's qualifications, personal qualities and professional activities. The study examines how pragmatic acts are expressed in the text of recommendations and the role of speech act theory in writing recommendations.

Keywords: Official-departmental speech style, recommendation letter, pragmat linguistics, speech act, locutionary act, illocutionary act, perlocutionary act, communicative purpose.

Today, we can see that the attention to the state language in our country is changing radically, as evidenced by the decisions and decrees adopted by the government to radically increase the prestige and status of the Uzbek language as the state language. [1] In this process, serious attention is being paid to working with official and departmental documents in official state organizations and departments. Considering that the official and departmental style of speech is a style of speech that serves social, legal relations in society, state and interstate official, political, economic, and cultural relations [8:12] and that official and departmental documents are important in organizing people's work activities, we can see that analyzing the texts of official documents, making effective use of the wide possibilities of language in working with them, and comprehensively studying and researching the scope of application of lexical and syntactic units used in such documents is more relevant than ever.

The official style is distinguished among the functional styles of the language by having various genres, and this style covers documents related to departmental work, legislation and diplomatic relations. M. Aminov, A. Madvaliyev, N. Mahkamov, N. Mahmudov in their book « Davlat tilida ish yuritish » divide documents related to work into organizational, order, informational documents and service correspondence according to the service position in administrative and managerial activities. [2: 24] These types of documents differ from each other in terms of lexical, morphological, syntactic features, scope, purpose and structure. For example, organizational documents reflect legal aspects such as the legal status of an organization or enterprise, its structural divisions and employees, and the recording of collective participation in the management process, while informational documents include such types of documents as applications, protocols, certificates, recommendations, and descriptions, which are aimed at exchanging information between individuals and legal

entities for various purposes. Therefore, we consider it appropriate to study the official texts of each of these document types separately from a pragmatic aspect.

We will focus this small study on the pragmatic aspect of the French texts of letters of recommendation, which are one of the most common types of information documents.

As is known, a letter of recommendation is a type of official document drawn up to recommend a person for a certain position or membership in various organizations. [2 : 305] A letter of recommendation can be issued by a specific legal entity or individual. The text of the letter of recommendation provides information about the qualifications, personal and moral qualities and activities of the recommended person as a specialist, and emphasizes that he is suitable for membership in the recommended position or organization. A letter of recommendation is similar to a description in its characteristics and is often in the form of a descriptive recommendation. The main difference between them is that a description notes the positive and negative characteristics of a person, while a letter of recommendation, along with his positive characteristics, expresses confidence in his ability to fulfill the tasks assigned to him in the future and recommends him. In France, a letter of recommendation (la lettre de recommandation) is one of the most common types of business documents[4], and in many cases, employers write letters of recommendation for former employees to transfer to a new job, and for students to participate in a grant, project, or employment, indicating their work experience, professional qualifications, personal and moral qualities. In French, letters of recommendation are also written in strict accordance with certain lexical, grammatical, and formal rules, without departing from the style of official business documents.

For this study, we selected real recommendation texts written in French by teachers of candidates participating in the «AMICIF» project published by the French organization «Lions Club de France» in different years, which were placed as examples on open Internet resources, and used them as analytical materials during our study. Also, in real recommendation letters, some parts of the personal information about the authors were changed in order to ensure the security of the authors' personal information.

The study of the pragmatic aspects and pragmatic features of the text of official and departmental business documents is becoming an object of research not only in the field of pragmalinguistics, but also in a number of disciplines such as stylistics, translation studies, and cultural studies. The pragmatic value of the text of official and departmental business documents requires the author to use linguistic means appropriately and expressively, with a specific purpose.

During pragmatic analysis, it is impossible to ignore the concept of speech act, which is one of the central concepts of pragmalinguistics and was put forward by the English philosopher J. Austin. In world linguistics, J. R. Searle, in French O. Ducrot, J. Anscombre, in Russian linguistics, V. N. Zabavnikov, A. N. Baranov, R. Conrad, A. Maslova, and in Uzbek linguistics, M. Hakimov, Sh. Safarov, M. Kurbanova, and others conducted research on the theory of speech act. For example, M. Hakimov assessed the speech act as "a statement of the relationship of mutual meaning acts that occur in the process of communication and interaction between people" [14:94], while Sh. Safarov considers the speech act as "... the pronunciation of a certain sentence in a specific communicative environment." [11:72]

It is known that J. Austin considered the substantive structure of a speech act to consist of the act of speaking (locutionary), the intention to speak (illocutive) and the acts of speech influence (perlocutionary). [3: 94-107]

Locution means «to make heard, to transmit, to listen, to receive». According to M. Khakimov, a locutionary act is the pronunciation of certain sounds and words taking into account the rules of the law and grammar of that language, and on this basis providing the expression with content and reference. [5: 155] The locutionary act occurs in official and departmental documents as the transmission of the author's thought to the recipient of the document. For example: Je suis certaine que son réel intérêt pour la France et ses études du français lui permettent de participer de façon très positive à votre stage. In this case, the candidate's interest in France and his/her study of French are indicative of his/her confidence that his/her ability to participate in the internship will allow him/her to do well. At the same time, there is also an illocutionary act in this sentence. The performers of the illocutionary act are the speaker or the author of the text, which occurs in the process of speech activity. [9:131] Considering that the illocutionary act is an explicit or implicit form of communicative intention inherent in the speaker's speech, in the above sentence, in addition to transmitting information, the author recommends and convinces the candidate as a participant in the internship, emphasizing that the candidate's positive qualities will bring them additional opportunities during the internship.

In the text of official and departmental documents, the author sometimes organizes his communicative intention in the form of indirect communication in order to achieve speech economy and encourage the recipient of the document to take some action. While the explicit statement of the expression forms direct speech acts, in indirect speech acts the communicative intention forms an implicit form of expression. [10:42-51] Many scientists have conducted scientific research on the description of indirect speech acts and the mechanism of indirect occurrence of speech structure. According to A. Maslova, "An indirect speech act is the manifestation of a second communicative intention under one illocutionary act." [7:63] It follows that the composition of indirect speech acts consists of two illocutionary acts. J. Searle called such two illocutionary acts primary and secondary illocutionary activities. [12:195-222] A. Shamakhmudova, who works in the field of pragmatics, stated that the primary illocutionary act expresses the true intention of a speech structure, while the secondary illocutionary act realizes the illocutionary act arising from its formal structure. [15:83-87] For example: J'ai pu également apprécier les qualités humaines de cet étudiant qui s'est tout de suite intégré au groupe que j'ai eu à ma charge. Ses atouts, outre sa formation, sont une ouverture d'esprit à d'autres cultures, son calme, sa motivation, sa curiosité font de lui un candidat parfait. In these linguistic units, the speaker highly values the candidate's positive qualities, stating that these qualities make him a good candidate, and secretly recommends this candidate for participation in the program. Here, the primary act is a description, the secondary illocutionary act is a recommendation. This situation demonstrates the polyintentional (multipurpose) nature of business documents.

Considering the above-mentioned characteristics of recommendations, the main illocutionary act in recommendations is the act of recommendation, and this act is often directly expressed in the text of recommendations. For example: « Pour toutes ces raisons, je vous recommande vivement Melle XXX S.T.P... », « Je recommande sans réserve sa candidature pour ce programme de formation... », « Je la parraine ainsi vivement pour le stage... ». In these examples, lexical units such as "vivement" and "sans réserve" indicate the strength of the recommendation given by the author.

In recommendations, acts of affirmation and attestation are mainly used to describe the candidate's professional skills and human qualities. For example: Par la présente, j'atteste que Darya XXX est une personne extraordinairement douée. Elle manifeste toujours ses progrès en français. Elle s'est montrée comme une étudiante sérieuse, consciencieuse, responsable, disponible, énergique.

One of the most important illocutionary speech acts that occurs in the text of recommendations is the act of persuasion. When performing the act of persuasion, the author, first of all, tries to show that he is a reliable person, that is, that he can be trusted. For example: « Je soussigné, Prabhjha XXX, fais partie de la famille AMICIF depuis plus de sept ans. Au cours de ces années, j'ai eu le plaisir de passer des moments inoubliables avec cette famille dans laquelle règnent la joie, l'amitié et l'unité. ». In the above example, the author has stated that he has been a member of the "AMICIF" program for more than 7 years and has given warm comments about this program. This shows that the author has full information about the requirements of the program and the results expected from it. In short, he can be a reliable person for the organizers of the program.

In the following example, the author mentions that he is a teacher at the French Alliance in the city where the candidate lives. This information indicates that the author's opinion about the candidate's professional skills and abilities is reliable and encourages the recipient to trust the author. « Je soussignée, Stéphanie Brémaud, directrice académique de l'Alliance Française de Lima, souhaite parrainer monsieur Diego XXX XXX XXX pour juillet 2022. » In another example, the author also mentions that he is the candidate's teacher and has known him since 2016, which indicates that the author of the document can be trusted. . « Professeur à l'Institut des langues étrangères de Samarkand, j'ai eu l'occasion de compter parmi mes élèves Monsieur ... entre de 2016 jusqu'à présent. »

Also, in order to further convince the recipient of the information they have provided and to take responsibility for the accuracy of the information provided, in some cases, the authors also put their signature and seal on the recommendation.

« Je suis sûre qu'il n'aura aucun difficulté d'intégrer et de communiqué dans un groupe multinational. » In this case, the author emphasizes that he is confident that the candidate will not encounter any difficulties in integrating and communicating in a multinational group. The author can also cite several examples of the candidate's achievements in his career to convince the recipient of the recommendation that the candidate's positive professional qualities are genuine. For example: Mlle. Bhavika XXX a fini ses études avec un Licence des études de Gestion. Elle a bien réussi DALF Cl avec 60.5/100. Currently she is pursuing courses of C1 ainsi que DU FLE (Diplôme Universitaire de Française Langue Etranger) with 14.50/20 à Alliance Française de Bombay.

In recommendations, the author, in addition to conveying information to the addressee and expressing his goals, also tries to influence him during the writing process. The author's goal is to emphasize the candidate's positive qualities and confidently confirm that he can make a significant contribution to the internship process with these qualities during the internship, while expecting a positive response from the person in charge. (...espère recevoir une réponse favorable de votre part... - I hope to receive a positive response from you...) Therefore, the text of recommendations has a perlocutionary character. Based on the essence of perlocution, recommendations, like other types of perlocutionary acts, perform "the act of influencing the mind, feelings and behavior of the listener". [11:72] In this case, the author

once again emphasizes the candidate's potential and thereby tries to influence the addressee to ensure his acceptance.

In conclusion, through the pragmalinguistic analysis of the texts of recommendations in French, it is found that locative, illocutionary and perlocutionary types of pragmatic acts in official and departmental documents are expressed using various syntactic forms. In the texts of recommendations, the author's intention is expressed through direct and indirect speech acts and an attempt is made to have a communicative impact on the addressee.

The main purpose of recommendations is to convince the addressee to support him by emphasizing the candidate's professional qualifications, personal and moral qualities. As illocutionary acts, the speech acts of recommendation and persuasion occupy a leading place in the texts of recommendations. While in direct acts the candidate's achievements, positive qualities and qualifications are openly stated, in indirect acts the author expresses his thoughts in a covert but powerful way.

The effective use of speech acts in recommendations, along with the inherent formality of the text, increases its effectiveness. Also, the author of the recommendation letter often demonstrates his or her position as a trusted person, instilling confidence in the recipient that the information written is accurate.

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